

Versioned Archive and Review of Biotic Interactions and Taxon Names Found within fgabriel1891/Plant-Frugivore-Interactions-SouthEastAsia

hash://md5/7d9225345bc83416b5aeebf3b13f68

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Abstract

Life on Earth is sustained by complex interactions between organisms and their environment. These biotic interactions can be captured in datasets and published digitally. We present a review and archiving process for such an openly accessible digital interactions dataset of known origin and discuss its outcome. The dataset under review, named fgabriel1891/Plant-Frugivore-Interactions-SouthEastAsia, has fingerprint hash://md5/7d9225345bc83416b5aeebf3b13f68, is 839KiB in size and contains 2,603 interactions with 1 unique type of association (e.g., eats) between 329 primary taxa (e.g., *Macaca fascicularis*) and 1,232 associated taxa (e.g., *Ficus nervosa*). This report includes detailed summaries of interaction data, a taxonomic review from multiple catalogs, and an archived version of the dataset from which the reviews are derived.

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Introduction

Data Review and Archive

Data review and archiving can be a time-consuming process, especially when done manually. This review report aims to help facilitate both activities. It automates the archiving of datasets, including Darwin Core archives, and is a citable backup of a version of the dataset. Additionally, an automatic review of species interaction claims made in the dataset is generated and registered with Global Biotic Interactions (J. H. Poelen, Simons, and Mungall 2014).

This review includes summary statistics about, and observations about, the dataset under review :

F. Gabriel. Muñoz. 2017. Palm-Animal frugivore associations extracted from literature with Biodiversity Observations Miner for SouthEast Asia. <https://github.com/fgabriel1891/Plant-Frugivore-Interactions-SouthEastAsia/archive/a733103ca98e82c11a081888006efad99f75ab84.zip> 2026-06-02T13:53:59.720Z hash://md5/7d9225345bc83416b5aeebf3b13f68

Methods

The review is performed through programmatic scripts that leverage tools like Preston (Elliott et al. 2025), Elton (Kuhn, Poelen, and Leinweber 2025), Nomer (Salim and Poelen 2025), globinizer (J. Poelen, Seltmann, and Mietchen 2024) combined with third-party tools like grep, mlr, tail and head.

Table 1: Tools used in this review process

tool name	version
preston	0.11.1
elton	0.16.11
nomer	0.6.5
globinizer	0.4.0
mlr	6.0.0
jq	1.6
yq	4.25.3
pandoc	3.1.6.1
duckdb	1.3.1
mapserver	7.6.4

The review process can be described in the form of the script below ¹.

```
# get versioned copy of the dataset (size approx. 839KiB) under review
elton pull fgabriel1891/Plant-Frugivore-Interactions-SouthEastAsia

# generate review notes
elton review fgabriel1891/Plant-Frugivore-Interactions-SouthEastAsia \
> review.tsv

# export indexed interaction records
elton interactions fgabriel1891/Plant-Frugivore-Interactions-SouthEastAsia \
> interactions.tsv

# export names and align them with the Catalogue of Life using Nomer
elton names fgabriel1891/Plant-Frugivore-Interactions-SouthEastAsia \
| nomer append col \
> name-alignment.tsv
```

or visually, in a process diagram.

You can find a copy of the full review script at [check-data.sh](https://github.com/fgabriel1891/check-data.sh). See also GitHub and Codeberg.

¹Note that you have to first get the data (e.g., via `elton pull fgabriel1891/Plant-Frugivore-Interactions-SouthEastAsia`) before being able to generate reviews (e.g., `elton review fgabriel1891/Plant-Frugivore-Interactions-SouthEastAsia`), extract interaction claims (e.g., `elton interactions fgabriel1891/Plant-Frugivore-Interactions-SouthEastAsia`), or list taxonomic names (e.g., `elton names fgabriel1891/Plant-Frugivore-Interactions-SouthEastAsia`)

Figure 1: Review Process Overview

Results

In the following sections, the results of the review are summarized ². Then, links to the detailed review reports are provided.

Files

An extensive list of files produced as part of the review process can be found in Appendix A. Review Files.

Archived Dataset

Note that *data.zip* file in this archive contains the complete, unmodified archived dataset under review.

Biotic Interactions

Figure 2: Biotic Interaction Data Model

In this review, biotic interactions (or biotic associations) are modeled as a primary (aka subject, source) organism interacting with an associate (aka object, target) organism. The dataset under review classified the primary/associate organisms with specific taxa. The primary and associate organisms The kind of interaction is documented as an interaction type.

The dataset under review, named fgabriel1891/Plant-Frugivore-Interactions-SouthEastAsia, has fingerprint hash://md5/7d9225345bc83416b5aeebf3b13f68,

²Disclaimer: The results in this review should be considered friendly, yet naive, notes from an unsophisticated robot. Please keep that in mind when considering the review results.

is 839KiB in size and contains 2,603 interactions with 1 unique type of association (e.g., eats) between 329 primary taxa (e.g., *Macaca fascicularis*) and 1,232 associated taxa (e.g., *Ficus nervosa*).

An exhaustive list of indexed interaction claims can be found in gzipped csv, tsv, geopackage and parquet archives. To facilitate discovery, a preview of claims available in the gzipped html page at indexed-interactions.html.gz are shown below.

The exhaustive list was used to create the following data summaries below.

Table 2: Sample of Indexed Interaction Claims

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Canis aureus	eats	Calamus rotang	David, J. P., Manakadan, R., & Ganesh, T. (2015). Frugivory and seed dispersal by birds and mammals in the coastal tropical dry evergreen forests of southern India: A review. <i>Tropical Ecology</i> , 56(1), 41-55.
Canis aureus	eats	Phoenix farinifera	David, J. P., Manakadan, R., & Ganesh, T. (2015). Frugivory and seed dispersal by birds and mammals in the coastal tropical dry evergreen forests of southern India: A review. <i>Tropical Ecology</i> , 56(1), 41-55.

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Viverricula indica	eats	Phoenix farinifera	David, J. P., Manakadan, R., & Ganesh, T. (2015). Frugivory and seed dispersal by birds and mammals in the coastal tropical dry evergreen forests of southern India: A review. Tropical Ecology, 56(1), 41-55.
Eudynamys scolopaceus	eats	Livinstona chinensis	David, J. P., Manakadan, R., & Ganesh, T. (2015). Frugivory and seed dispersal by birds and mammals in the coastal tropical dry evergreen forests of southern India: A review. Tropical Ecology, 56(1), 41-55.

Table 3: Most Frequently Mentioned Interaction Types (up to 20 most frequent)

interactionTypeName	count
eats	2603

Table 4: Most Frequently Mentioned Primary Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	count
Macaca fascicularis	258

sourceTaxonName	count
Elephas maximus	96
Helarctos malayanus	95
Eulemur fulvus collaris	77
Homo sapiens	63
Maxomys surifer	55
Nasalis larvatus	53
Nomascus gabriellae	52
Gorilla gorilla	49
Hylobates muelleri	48
Macaca leonina	43
Paradoxurus hermaphroditus	36
Hypsiprymnodon moschatus	35
Pteropus giganteus	34
Ducula badia	34
Treron curvirostra	34
Treron phoenicoptera	33
Macaca tonkeana	33
Menetes berdmorei	33

Table 5: Most Frequently Mentioned Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

targetTaxonName	count
Ficus nervosa	26
Bischofia javanica	24
Gironniera nervosa	22
Ficus subcordata	22
Brahea armata	22
Aglaia spectabilis	22
Ilex chevalieri	21
Ficus altissima	20
Cinnamomum camphora	19
Aidia densiflora	18
Ficus	17
Syzygium	17
Eurya nitida	17
Ficus beteropleura	15
Macaranga tanarius	15
Ficus benjamina	14
Ligustrum lucidum	14
Canarium euphyllum	13
Ficus benghalensis	12

Table 6: Most Frequent Interactions between Primary and Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
Canis aureus	eats	Phoenix farinifera	5
Macaca leonina	eats	Baccaurea ramiflora	4
Syconycteris australis	eats	Schefflera actinophylla	4
Viverricula indica	eats	Phoenix farinifera	3
Macaca leonina	eats	Garcinia benthamii	3
Canis aureus	eats	Cordia dichotoma	3
Canis aureus	eats	Memecylon umbellatum	3
Pteropus giganteus	eats	Opilia amanitaceae	3
Tapirus terrestris	eats	Syagrus romanzoffiana	3
Helarctos malayanus	eats	Ficus	3
Nycticebus coucang	eats	Eugeissona tristis	3
Callosciurus finlaysonii	eats	Aglaiia spectabilis	3
Syconycteris australis	eats	Syzygium cormiflorum	3
Canis aureus	eats	Calamus rotang	2
Macaca leonina	eats	Gnetum macrostachyum	2
Macaca leonina	eats	Ficus	2
Macaca leonina	eats	Ziziphus attopensis	2
Hylobates lar	eats	Platymitra macrocarpa	2
Hylobates lar	eats	Nephelium melliferum	2

Interaction Networks

The figures below provide a graph view on the dataset under review. The first shows a summary network on the kingdom level, and the second shows how interactions on the family level. It is important to note that both network graphs were first aligned taxonomically using the Catalogue of Life. Please refer to the original (or verbatim) taxonomic names for a more original view on the interaction data.

Figure 3: Interactions on taxonomic kingdom rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life download svg

You can download the indexed dataset under review at indexed-interactions.csv.gz. A tab-separated file can be found at indexed-interactions.tsv.gz

Figure 4: Interactions on the taxonomic family rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life. [download svg](#)

Geospatial Distribution

If geospatial information was extracted from the dataset under review, the map below will show their distribution. These maps were generated using MapServer (McKenna et al. 2025) tools configured via map configuration indexed-interactions.map :

```
MAP
  SIZE 1600 800
  EXTENT -180 -90 180 90
  PROJECTION
    "init=epsg:4326"
  END
  LAYER # MODIS WMS map from NASA
    NAME "modis_nasa"
    TYPE RASTER
    OFFSITE 0 0 0
    STATUS ON
    CONNECTIONTYPE WMS
    CONNECTION "https://gibs.earthdata.nasa.gov/wms/epsg4326/best/wms.cgi?"

  METADATA
    "wms_srs" "EPSG:4326"
    "wms_name" "OSM_Land_Water_Map"
    "wms_server_version" "1.1.1"
    "wms_format" "image/jpeg"
  END
  CLASS
    STYLE
      COLOR 232 232 232
      OUTLINECOLOR 32 32 32
    END
  END
  LAYER
    NAME "indexed-interactions"
    TYPE POLYGON
    STATUS ON
    CONNECTIONTYPE OGR
    CONNECTION "indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg"
    DATA "indexed-interactions-h3"
    CLASS
      STYLE
        COLORRANGE 253.0 231.0 37.0 32.0 164.0 134.0
        DATARANGE NULL NULL
        RANGEITEM "log_number_of_records"
```

```

        OUTLINECOLOR 0 0 0
      END
    END
  END
END

```

Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Figure 5: Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Associated data can be found in the geopackage files at indexed-interactions.gpkg for point data and indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg for data clustered in geospatial h3 hexagonals.

Learn more about the structure of this download at GloBI website, by opening a GitHub issue, or by sending an email.

Another way to discover the dataset under review is by searching for it on the GloBI website.

Taxonomic Alignment

As part of the review, all names are aligned against various name catalogs (e.g., col, ncbi, discoverlife, gbif, itis, wfo, mdd, tpt, pbdb, and worms). These alignments can help review name usage or aid in selecting of a suitable taxonomic name resource.

Table 7: Sample of Name Alignments

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Aburria jacutinga	SYNONYM_OF	col	Pipile jacutinga
Acacia auriculiformis	NONE	col	Acacia auriculiformis
Acacia auriculiformis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Acacia auriculiformis
Acacia concinna	SYNONYM_OF	col	Senegalia rugata

Table 8: Distribution of Taxonomic Ranks of Aligned Names by Catalog. Names that were not aligned with a catalog are counted as NAs. So, the total number of unaligned names for a catalog will be listed in their NA row.

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	NA	282
col	family	16
col	genus	140
col	species	1075
col	subgenus	1
col	subspecies	16
col	variety	9
discoverlife	NA	1526
gbif	NA	282
gbif	family	15
gbif	genus	141
gbif	species	1075
gbif	subspecies	17
gbif	variety	13
itis	NA	1002
itis	family	14
itis	genus	93
itis	species	416
itis	subgenus	1
itis	variety	2
mdd	NA	1526
ncbi	NA	472
ncbi	family	12
ncbi	genus	133
ncbi	species	906
ncbi	subspecies	1
ncbi	varietas	2
pbdb	NA	1284
pbdb	family	13
pbdb	genus	89
pbdb	species	140
tpt	NA	1291
tpt	family	2
tpt	genus	10
tpt	species	223
wfo	NA	569
wfo	family	10
wfo	genus	124
wfo	species	812

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
wfo	subspecies	9
wfo	variety	9
worms	NA	1403
worms	family	7
worms	genus	43
worms	species	73

Table 9: Name relationship types per catalog. Name relationship type “NONE” means that a name was not recognized by the associated catalog. “SAME_AS” indicates either a “HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME” or “SYNONYM_OF” name relationship type. We recognize that “SYNONYM_OF” encompasses many types of nomenclatural synonymies (ICZN 1999) (e.g., junior synonym, senior synonyms).

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	SYNONYM_OF	517
col	NONE	284
col	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1085
discoverlife	NONE	1552
gbif	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1245
gbif	NONE	284
gbif	SYNONYM_OF	587
itis	SYNONYM_OF	72
itis	NONE	1008
itis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	497
mdd	NONE	1462
mdd	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	88
mdd	SYNONYM_OF	2
ncbi	SYNONYM_OF	111
ncbi	NONE	475
ncbi	SAME_AS	979
pbdb	NONE	1291
pbdb	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	256
pbdb	SYNONYM_OF	13
tpt	NONE	1316
tpt	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	229
tpt	SYNONYM_OF	7
wfo	NONE	572
wfo	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	813
wfo	SYNONYM_OF	271
wfo	HAS_UNCHECKED_NAME	37

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
worms	NONE	1419
worms	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	134
worms	SYNONYM_OF	22

Table 10: List of Available Name Alignment Reports

catalog name	alignment results
col	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
ncbi	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
discoverlife	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
gbif	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
itis	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
wfo	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
mdd	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
tpt	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
pbdb	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
worms	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

Additional Reviews

Elton, Nomer, and other tools may have difficulties interpreting existing species interaction datasets. Or, they may misbehave, or otherwise show unexpected behavior. As part of the review process, detailed review notes are kept that document possibly misbehaving, or confused, review bots. An sample of review notes associated with this review can be found below.

Table 11: First few lines in the review notes.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-06-03T08:16:01Z	note	invalid date string [Kumara, H. N., & Singh, M. (2004). The influence of differing hunting practices on the relative abundance of mammals in two rainforest areas of the Western Ghats, India. Oryx, 38(3), 321-327.]
2026-06-03T08:16:01Z	note	invalid date string [Kumara, H. N., & Singh, M. (2004). The influence of differing hunting practices on the relative abundance of mammals in two rainforest areas of the Western Ghats, India. Oryx, 38(3), 321-327.]
2026-06-03T08:16:01Z	note	invalid date string [Kumara, H. N., & Singh, M. (2004). The influence of differing hunting practices on the relative abundance of mammals in two rainforest areas of the Western Ghats, India. Oryx, 38(3), 321-327.]
2026-06-03T08:16:01Z	note	invalid date string [Kumara, H. N., & Singh, M. (2004). The influence of differing hunting practices on the relative abundance of mammals in two rainforest areas of the Western Ghats, India. Oryx, 38(3), 321-327.]

In addition, you can find the most frequently occurring notes in the table below.

Table 12: Most frequently occurring review notes, if any.

reviewComment	count
invalid date string [Kumara, H. N., & Singh, M. (2004). The influence of differing hunting practices on the relative abundance of mammals in two rainforest areas of the Western Ghats, India. <i>Oryx</i> , 38(3), 321-327.]	4

For additional information on review notes, please have a look at the first 500 Review Notes in html format or the download full gzipped csv or tsv archives.

GloBI Review Badge

As part of the review, a review badge is generated. This review badge can be included in webpages to indicate the review status of the dataset under review.

Figure 6: Picture of a GloBI Review Badge ³

Note that if the badge is green, no review notes were generated. If the badge is yellow, the review bots may need some help with interpreting the species interaction data.

GloBI Index Badge

If the dataset under review has been registered with GloBI, and has been successfully indexed by GloBI, the GloBI Index Status Badge will turn green. This means that the dataset under review was indexed by GloBI and is available through GloBI services and derived data products.

Figure 7: Picture of a GloBI Index Badge ⁴

If you'd like to keep track of reviews or index status of the dataset under review, please visit GloBI's dataset index ⁵ for badge examples.

³Up-to-date status of the GloBI Review Badge can be retrieved from the GloBI Review Depot

⁴Up-to-date status of the GloBI Index Badge can be retrieved from GloBI's API

⁵At time of writing (2026-06-03) the version of the GloBI dataset index was available at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/datasets>

Discussion

This review and archive provides a means of creating citable versions of datasets that change frequently. This may be useful for dataset managers, including natural history collection data managers, as a backup archive of a shared Darwin Core archive. It also serves as a means of creating a trackable citation for the dataset in an automated way, while also including some information about the contents of the dataset.

This review aims to provide a perspective on the dataset to aid in understanding of species interaction claims discovered. However, it is important to note that this review does *not* assess the quality of the dataset. Instead, it serves as an indication of the open-ness⁶ and FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Trekels et al. 2023) of the dataset: to perform this review, the data was likely openly available, **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. The current Open-FAIR assessment is qualitative, and a more quantitative approach can be implemented with specified measurement units.

This report also showcases the reuse of machine-actionable (meta)data, something highly recommended by the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Making (meta)data machine-actionable enables more precise processing by computers, enabling even naive review bots like Nomer and Elton to interpret the data effectively. This capability is crucial for not just automating the generation of reports, but also for facilitating seamless data exchanges, promoting interoperability.

Acknowledgements

We thank the many humans that created us and those who created and maintained the data, software and other intellectual resources that were used for producing this review. In addition, we are grateful for the natural resources providing the basis for these human and bot activities. Also, thanks to <https://github.com/zygoballus> for helping improve the layout of the review tables.

Author contributions

Nomer was responsible for name alignments. Elton carried out dataset extraction, and generated the review notes. Preston tracked, versioned, and packaged, the dataset under review.

⁶According to <http://opendefinition.org/>: “Open data is data that can be freely used, reused and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike.”

Appendix A. Review Files

The following files are produced in this review:

filename	description
biblio.bib	list of bibliographic reference of this review
check-dataset.sh	data review workflow/process as expressed in a bash script
data.zip	a versioned archive of the data under review
HEAD	the digital signature of the data under review
index.docx	review in MS Word format
index.html	review in HTML format
index.md	review in Pandoc markdown format
index.pdf	review in PDF format
indexed-citations.csv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped comma-separated values file format
indexed-citations.html.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interactions claims in gzipped html file format
indexed-citations.tsv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions-col-family-col-family.svg	network diagram showing the taxon family to taxon family interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions-col-kingdom-col-kingdom.svg	network diagram showing the taxon kingdom to taxon kingdom interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions.csv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-interactions.html.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-interactions.tsv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions.parquet	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-interactions.png	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review plotted on a map
indexed-interactions.map	mapserver configuration to plot species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review on a map
indexed-interactions.gpkg	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg	geospatially clustered h3 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-sample.csv	list of species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions-sample.html	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in html format
indexed-interactions-sample.tsv	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
indexed-names.csv.gz	taxonomic names indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-names.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-col.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-col.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-itis.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-worms.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-sample.csv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
indexed-names-sample.html	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in html format
indexed-names-sample.tsv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
interaction.svg	diagram summarizing the data model used to index species interaction claims
nanopub-sample.trig	first 500 species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)

filename	description
nanopub.trig.gz	species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
process.svg	diagram summarizing the data review processing workflow
prov.nq	origin of the dataset under review as expressed in rdf/nquads
review.csv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
review.html.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped html format
review.tsv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
review-sample.csv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
review-sample.html	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in html format
review-sample.tsv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
review.svg	a review badge generated as part of the dataset review process
zenodo.json	metadata of this review expressed in Zenodo record metadata

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